

Case study: BA 286 & BA 12

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ABBREVIATIONS

CDC Centre of Disease Control

ABSTRACT

A review of two Airbus A380 flights is provided that involved reported contaminated air via the aircraft air supply system. Details of the flight, short- and longer-term effects on the crew and key flight safety implications are provided. The pattern of effects identified are consistent with those seen in other contaminated air events, with a clear need for airline operational improvements and a suitable medical protocol to be developed.

INTRODUCTION

The pattern of effects in the two cited incidents are consistent with contaminated air exposure on aircraft and those identified in Michaelis *et al* (2017).^{1,2} It is therefore very likely that a contaminated air event related to the bleed air system occurred and not at all unsurprising that no fault was identified. There is a clear need for a suitable medical protocol for such events. Improved reporting is required, with the Global Cabin Air Reporting System (GCARS) that is in development being a recommended international reporting tool. There is an urgent need for aircraft air detection systems to be fitted as per CS 25.1309c. Flight safety was degraded in these incidents and numerous shortcomings were highlighted. Both short and long-term adverse health effects were reported. A more thorough investigation is definitely warranted as safety lessons can be learned.

Case studies

1. BA 286: Airbus A380

A British Airways flight, BA 286 departed San Francisco for London Heathrow on 25 October, 2016. There were 433 people on board the A380, consisting of 25 crew and 408 passengers. Approximately one hour after departure the captain reported to air traffic control that there were “toxic fumes, toxic gas type fumes” in the aircraft.^{3,4} While overhead Alberta, the initial decision was made to divert to Calgary, however this was amended to Vancouver (YVR) due to increased ground support for the large Airbus A380 at YVR.

A Canadian Civil Aviation Daily Occurrence System (CADORS) reports that “*due to sickness with some crew and passengers*” the aircraft dumped fuel, declared a PAN call and diverted to YVR.⁵ The report describes “*a strong noxious smell located near the number 4 main cabin door and upper flight deck galley.*” The report categorization was listed under smoke/fumes in aircraft, crew incapacitation, medical emergency, fuel, declared emergency/priority and diversion.

All 25 aircrew were sent to hospital as a precautionary action, with three crew and one passenger requiring medical attention. All were subsequently released.

British Airways and Airbus inspected the aircraft in YVR, but no fault was identified and the aircraft was flown back to the UK with flight crew and maintenance personnel only. In flight troubleshooting identified no faults and the aircraft was subsequently released for further service.⁵

The author as a qualified air accident investigator and an expert in cabin air contamination was asked by the Global Cabin Air Quality Executive (GCAQE) to undertake a debriefing session with a number of the crew in the UK over the following 10 days, while blood was drawn. The following facts were

Symptom category	Acute	Short-term	Medium-term	Long-term*
Neurological	15	12	9	5
Central Nervous System	13	11	8	2
Peripheral Nervous System	9	3	3	3
Neurobehavioral	12	8	8	3
Gastrointestinal	10	8	7	0
Respiratory	8	8	8	4
Cardiovascular	6	9	8	2
General	4	9	9	5
Irritant	8	4	2	0

Table 1 — Symptoms for BA 286 and BA 12

established.

Many of the cabin crew in various areas of the aircraft reported a strong noxious /intoxicating fume smell. Eleven of the 25 aircrew were affected to varying degrees ranging from nausea and a metallic taste to incapacitation. Oxygen was used by at least one of the pilots. A number of passengers reported the fumes, described by one as “someone with their shoes off” with some reporting adverse effects.³ Paramedics met the aircraft on arrival to monitor the crew and passengers requiring help. One passenger advised that they were told they would need to pay \$800 CAD to go to hospital as the airline did not have the cash available to assist them to be examined in hospital.³

Blood was drawn from 12 crew and three passengers in order for it to be tested by the Centre of Disease Control (CDC) in the US based upon their protocol looking for ortho-cresyl phosphate adducts to butyrylcholinesterase in human serum.^{6,7}

2. BA 12: Airbus A380

An Airbus A380 aircraft departed Singapore for London on November 9, 2016. On take-off some of the cabin crew reported a fume event described as ‘dirty/smelly socks’. The pilots contacted Medlink, upon which anxiety was suggested by the flight deck to be the cause. A cabin crew member who was assisting a cardiologist doctor/passenger onboard reported that this was denied by the doctor who assessed the affected aircrew. Ativan/lorazepam was suggested by Medlink but was refused by the affected cabin crew. The flight was continued for the 13-hour flight to London. Five cabin crew undertook the debriefing by the author and had their blood drawn in a similar manner to the BA286 crew.

RESULTS

The range of symptoms for both BA 286 and BA 12 can be seen in Table 1.

Long-term effects were ten months + after fume event / Only eight crew followed up to date.

Return to work timeframe	Number of people	Comments on range of long-term effects remaining at 10 months
Immediate -1 month	4	1- numerous 2 - some 1 - none
>1 month -6 months	1	1- some
>6 months-10 months	2	2 -numerous
Still off work	1	1 -numerous

Table 2 — Crew Long-Term Effects at 10-Month Follow-Up

Various other points of interest are listed below:

- A smell/ fume was identified by 12 of the 20 crew (three passengers) interviewed.
- The smell was described as that of dirty socks. Sweaty socks, toxic smell, glue, plastic smell, cheesy smell....
- Six crew were incapacitated
- Oxygen was used by nine+ cabin crew
- Most paramedics tests found no abnormalities
- All (limited) tests at the hospital were assessed as normal
- Previous events: three of the crew reported previous major events, two reported fume events as regular and one reported them as occasional
- Most of the crew advised there was no training for fume events
- Most of the crew had been flying for many years
- BA12 crew experienced increased range of effects and longer-term than BA 12, perhaps as the flight was not diverted.

Eight of the 17 crew were followed up ten months after the events. The findings are outlined in Table 2. All except one crewmember had returned to work, with a number of the crew reporting on-going longer-term effects. Three of the seven crew that had returned to work reported

numerous longer-term effects remaining, while three reported some effects remaining at the 10-month review.

Investigation

The official investigations undertaken by Airbus and the airline indicated that no fault was found (NFF) with the aircraft. Unofficially some of the crew advised that the Vancouver emergency services identified higher readings at the rear of the aircraft. The aircraft was ferried home the following day. No AAIB (Aircraft Accident Investigation Branch) investigation was undertaken as the airline and manufacturer advised that no fault had been found. This is despite the AAIB being required to investigate serious incidents under the EU Regulation 996/2010. Safety investigation authorities may decide to investigate incidents “when they expect to draw safety lessons from them.”⁸

Serious incidents include those requiring emergency use of oxygen by the pilots, flight crew (pilot) incapacitation in flight, fires and smoke in flight, injury to internal organs and hospitalization for more than 48 hours within seven days of the incident.

The investigation for BA 12 was reported to finding no fault or NFF. It was unofficially reported that staining was found in the No. 3 engine. No AAIB investigation was undertaken.

Limitations of the case study

A number of limitations apply to the information collated from the debriefings including:

- Not all crew responded. On BA 286, 12 of the 25 crew undertook the debrief, while only five of the 25 crew on BA 12 participated;
- The information received was not complete in all cases;
- There were no on-board detection systems despite the EASA certification standard CS-25 1309C requiring “Information concerning unsafe system operating conditions must be provided to the crew to enable them to take appropriate corrective action. A warning indication must be provided if immediate corrective action is required. Systems.”
- Crew reluctance to provide complete information due to employment pressure;
- Access to maintenance records not available;
- Crew difficulty in getting medical support. Crew advised their general physician advised this was an occupational issue necessitating them to see their airline doctor or that they would help but did not recognize aerotoxic syndrome as a valid medical disease. Airline doctors were reported to have advised aerotoxic syndrome and fume related illness was not valid and they could not help;
- This study warrants further investigation and support.

Blood testing

The CDC in Atlanta volunteered to test the crew and passenger blood based on their published protocol.⁶ All costs were to be covered by the CDC. The CDC however required a government authority from either Canada, the USA or the UK to request the testing to be undertaken by the CDC. No government authority in the three countries would give permission. Those contacted included Transport Canada, Transport Safety Bureau in Canada, Public Health Canada, NTSB, FAA, Public Health England, AAIB (UK), CAA (UK).

The CAA advised in May 2017 that it would not give permission to CDC for the following reasons as an agreed outcome between the CDC and CAA.⁹

- The oCP-BChE adducts test is a scientifically validated test, i.e. it has been shown to be an effective method for measuring oCP-BChE adducts
- The test has not yet been clinically validated, i.e. the normal range in the general population / target populations has not been established or correlated with exposure to ortho isomers of TCP and we therefore do not know the clinical significance of a result in an individual subject
- The test is potentially of clinical value and therefore we have an interest in trying to facilitate scientific research that would help to validate this
- This would initially require a study of exposed subjects in an environment where the concentrations can readily be monitored and with a suitable non-exposed control group; it is likely that this work would be undertaken in either production or maintenance facilities

There has not yet been an opportunity to take this work forward, but I hope that it will be possible to engage with industry and to develop a research project with CDC in the foreseeable future—unfortunately I cannot give any timescale at the moment. Given that the test is not yet clinically validated, the UK CAA is not able support the testing of blood samples taken from crew on flights where fume events have been reported.”

However, it should be noted that Liyasova (2011), Schopfer (2014), Tacal (2014) were all research projects that have subsequently been published.^{7,10,11}

Is No fault found unusual?

It is very common after aircraft fume events that the investigations report no fault is found (NFF). A few examples include:

- EASA (2017) – “Of particular interest are the secondary TCAC-events, as these are fed from deposits. Inspection the checking of the engines after a TCAC-event can therefore lead to no findings.... The exact causes for the spontaneous release of pollutants from such deposits are still unclear It is conceivable that mechanical or thermal stress or

the introduction of solvents such as water or de-icing agents can trigger such an event.” TCAC = Technical Cabin Air Contamination with the origin in deposited oil contaminants inside the bleed air system and the air conditioning system.¹²

- Airbus (2013) - “ With lower levels of contamination the reports are often only associated with odors in the cabin. ... It is often difficult to immediately identify the exact source of contamination and without obvious signs such as abnormally high oil consumption, it is not uncommon to apply inappropriate maintenance action. ... There are of course already documented trouble shooting procedures although these are again usually more efficient in the case of heavy oil leakage. In the case of very light oil contamination it is very difficult to confirm leakage by the defined inspection procedures.”¹³
- CAA (2017) - Engine bleed air related incidents: “such events can be transient and it may not be possible for airlines to determine the specific source.”¹⁴

CONCLUSIONS

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